

What Makes a Virtual Celebrity Agent Trustworthy in VR? Exploring the Role of Stylization and Voice

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Fig. 1: An overview of our study. Participants first watched a real video clip of Sheldon's speech in VR, followed by virtual Sheldon agents with three visual styles (*Hand-sculpted*, *AI-reconstructed*, and *Non-stylized*) and two voice types (*Cloned* and *Synthesized*). This study investigates how *Style* and *Voice* shape trust in virtual celebrity agents compared to video-based representations.

Abstract—Recent advances in generative AI have accelerated the deployment of virtual celebrity agents for commercial endorsements. However, little is known about how their visual style and vocal type, especially when these characteristics are generated via advanced AI reconstruction or voice cloning techniques, affect user trust, perceived realism, familiarity, and social presence. We extracted a representative clip of Sheldon Cooper from *The Big Bang Theory* as a baseline and generated multiple Sheldon virtual agents that varied in visual style (hand-sculpted, AI-reconstructed, or non-stylized) and vocal type (cloned or synthesized). A 3×2 within-subjects experiment ($N = 30$) revealed that visual style significantly affected user trust, perceived realism, familiarity, and social presence, while vocal type affected only perceived realism and familiarity. Comparisons between the virtual agents and the video baseline confirmed that even cutting-edge 3D modeling still differs significantly from authentic video representations. Behavioral data indicate that the relationship between interpersonal-distance variations and trust levels is not a simple linear one. These findings provide actionable guidance for designers leveraging generative AI to create trustworthy virtual avatars or agents and delineate new research avenues for virtual celebrity agents.

Index Terms—Trust, Virtual agent, Celebrity agent, Virtual human, Virtual reality

1 INTRODUCTION

Virtual humans, as perceptible representations of real human in virtual environments, are widely used in the form of avatars or agents in VR [24]. Improved visual and behavioral realism has made virtual agents and avatars widely adopted in online education [9, 13, 23], commercial recommendation [38, 43, 53], and healthcare [8, 39]. At the

same time, with the rise of the Metaverse, celebrities have begun to create their own virtual agents or avatars in the virtual world [64]. As virtual counterparts of human celebrities, they not only inherit personal attributes but also exhibit amplified traits unique to the virtual domain, particularly in commercial applications [16, 22, 56]. Unlike generic agents, they leverage the parasocial relationships developed through long-term media exposure to shape user perceptions [40]. However, the specific impacts of such celebrity agents on user perception remains unclear, especially in VR.

Stylization refers to the broadest spectrum of visual variation in virtual agents and avatars [8]. Ordered by ascending visual fidelity, their styles range from abstract depictions such as stick figures and sketches [17, 28, 66], to mid-level styles such as cartoons or simplified forms [50, 60], and finally to highly detailed and photorealistic renderings [20, 42, 48]. Recent advances in generative AI have enabled efficient production of stylized virtual humans while maintaining visual quality, offering new potential for creating celebrity agents. Yet, current research on virtual celebrities focused mainly on commercial endorsements, often comparing them with real celebrities while overlooking the influence of their own characteristics [64]. As the first impression of an agent, visual style can strongly shape perceptions [61], but its impact on celebrity

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agents under AI-driven stylization remains underexplored.

Vocal cues constitute another critical channel through which agents convey information, with voice quality being a pivotal factor [51]. Typically, matching voice quality with visual fidelity helps to enhance perceived likability [10], credibility [54], and even personality traits [55], while mitigating the uncanny valley effect caused by audio-visual mismatch [25,34]. Thanks to recent advances in AI-based voice generation, voice cloning techniques now achieve far higher quality than traditional Text-to-Speech (TTS) methods [19]. For celebrity agents, this technology allows a celebrity agent’s voice to closely match the original, achieving greater behavioral consistency. However, current research has not clarified which visual styles best match AI-cloned voices or how this (mis)match shapes perception of AI-stylized celebrity agents.

While technologies such as AI-driven stylization and voice cloning have undoubtedly improved production efficiency, they also raise questions of credibility and trust, especially when deployed in high-stakes contexts [45]. Within the CASA (Computers Are Social Actors) paradigm, trust in virtual agents essentially mirrors interpersonal trust [27,36]. Higher trust levels have been shown to enhance learning motivation [9], influence decision-making in gaming contexts [29], and facilitate international online transactions [6]. Regarding celebrity agents, their social influence and celebrity status make user trust vital as a guard against malicious acts like fraud and rumor-mongering. However, few studies have examined how AI stylization and voice cloning jointly influence trust in celebrity agents.

This study investigates how advanced AI-based stylization, combined with AI-cloned voices, shapes users’ trust in celebrity agents, along with related perceptions of realism, familiarity, and social presence. We also examine which visual styles best align with AI-cloned voices and how user perceptions of these combinations differ from those of authentic video representations. [3]. Additionally, we explore the relationship between interpersonal distance and trust in agent-mediated interactions [11,46]. To address these questions, we selected Sheldon Cooper from *The Big Bang Theory*. His high recognizability fosters parasocial relationships, which in turn shape viewers’ trust and other related perceptions. We created several virtual agents of him with different visual styles (hand-sculpted, AI-reconstructed, or non-stylized) and vocal types (cloned or synthesized), and conducted a 3×2 within-subjects user study.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 discusses related work in the scope of the article. Section 3 details the experiment in which we evaluate the effects of *Style* and *Voice* on users. The results are presented in Section 4 and discussed in Section 5. Section 6 addresses the limitations of the current study and directions for future research. Section 7 concludes the article and gives an overview of future work.

2 RELATED WORK

2.1 Celebrity Agents and Stylized Agents

Celebrity agents inherit the influence of their real-world counterparts and often outperform ordinary agents, especially in commercial domains [64]. Song and Shin [53] found that adopting a celebrity’s appearance in e-commerce chatbots helps mitigate uncanny valley effects. Belanche et al. [5] compared the endorsements of human and virtual influencers, finding that virtual influencers were more effective in promoting utilitarian products by focusing on rationality, professionalism, and consistency. In negotiation, celebrity appearances can significantly shape users’ strategies, making them more willing to compromise and cooperate [58].

Stylized agents primarily rely on visual fidelity to convey information and shape user perceptions. A large-scale experiment has shown that photorealistic agents are generally preferred in VR [67]. Amadou et al. [1] demonstrated that realistic virtual characters can elicit higher levels of social presence and attractiveness, as well as users’ perception of emotional expressiveness. However, agents or avatars with medium or low-level realism designs (e.g., sketch, abstract, iconic, cartoon) [61], may perform equally in some contexts. For example, in high-stress VR scenarios, Lugin et al. [28] reported that iconic avatars performed comparably to realistic avatars in both task performance and presence,

while demanding fewer resources. In medical contexts, where trust in virtual agents is critical, medium-realistic physician agents were rated as trustworthy as highly realistic ones [8].

While previous stylization methods require time-consuming artistic work, recent AI algorithms can automatically stylize virtual agents and avatars, significantly reducing manual effort. For instance, Sang et al. [49] proposed AgileAvatar, which generates cartoon-style avatars from selfies with matched bodies. Also, Men et al. [33] introduced 3DToonify, which transforms 2D images into avatars with hand-drawn or Pixar-like styles. Photorealistic styles often use a 3D reconstruction method. Lei et al. [26] developed the Hierarchical Representation Network (HRN), which extracts textures from portraits and reconstructs photorealistic facial meshes.

However, few studies have investigated the role of celebrity agents beyond commercial domains or examined the effect of stylized celebrity agents, particularly when AI-driven stylization techniques are employed.

2.2 Vocal Cues in Virtual Agents

Vocal cues such as pitch, timbre, speech rate, and voice quality critically shape users’ perceptions of virtual agents [51]. For example, Parmar et al. [39] found that human voices were rated more trustworthy, likable, and professional than synthetic ones in health persuasion. Mania et al. [31] demonstrated that high vocal dominance (high volume, low pitch, confident tone) reduced perceived fairness in negotiation. And Higgins et al. [20] reported that pairing realistic appearances with synthetic voices in virtual agents weakened users’ social presence, though not empathy.

Among these cues, voice quality stands out as a particularly crucial factor. AI-based voice cloning has achieved high-fidelity replication of any speaker’s timbre. Arik et al. [2] proposed two neural approaches for few-shot voice cloning, balancing similarity and speed. Building on this, Neekhara et al. [37] introduced a model that allows fine-grained control over prosody, rhythm, and emotion. More recently, Transformer-based large models, such as CosyVoice [14], have delivered human-level naturalness, low latency, and near-lossless quality in streaming synthesis. These advances have also begun to impact VR research and applications. For instance, Kao et al. [23] found that avatars with voices that resemble players increased immersion and learning motivation in an educational VR game. Additionally, Okano et al. [38] discovered that mimicking the voice of customers enhanced the rapport and familiarity in customer service scenarios.

Yet, little research has investigated how cloned celebrity voices in VR agents shape user perceptions.

2.3 Trust in Virtual Agents and Affecting Factors

The formation of trust between humans and virtual agents parallels interpersonal trust and depends heavily on verbal and non-verbal behaviors such as appearance and voice [27,36].

Regarding visual appearance, Caneles et al. [8] found that the stylistic designs of a doctor agent had no significant effect on users’ trust in medical advice. Extending this to a general public speaking context, Gao et al. [18] reported that realistic agent styles could enhance participants’ trust in presented content, although the effect remained limited. In trust games, agents’ facial expressions, especially positive ones, have been shown to enhance participants’ trust and influence decisions [29]. Voice has also been examined in several studies. For example, Qiu and Benbasat [43] found that the presence of TTS voice significantly enhanced both cognitive and affective trust in customer service avatars. Moreover, Tolmeijer et al. [57] observed that revealing the gender through voice does not affect users’ trust. On the other hand, Elkins and Derrick [15] found a negative correlation between agents’ voice pitch and users’ trust, although this relationship varied over time.

Trust is also linked to behavioral factors and other perceptions. Interpersonal distance, defined as the physical space between individuals, has been widely regarded as a behavioral indicator of trust. For instance, Rosenberger et al. [46] reported in a repeated trust game experiment that greater interpersonal distance was positively correlated with psychological distance. In contrast, Clements et al. [11] observed a weak

effect that more trustworthy agents could lead to increased interpersonal distance in a wayfinding task. In terms of perceptual factors, studies have found that users’ sense of social presence is positively correlated with their trust in recommendation agents [44]. Similarly, trust is strengthened when agents are able to convey empathy, particularly for older users [21].

Despite these insights, few studies have investigated how stylized celebrity agents with cloned voices affect user trust, as well as how such manipulations affect interpersonal distance in VR contexts.

3 METHOD

This section presents the experimental design, the creation of experimental stimuli, and the detailed study procedure. An overview of the study flow and experimental conditions is provided in Figure 1.

3.1 Experiment Design

Based on the identified research gap, we first selected a human celebrity as the target for our study. We chose Dr. Sheldon Cooper (from The Big Bang Theory TV series) as the celebrity subject, given his recognizable intelligence, personality, and popularity. Moreover, as a fictional character, Sheldon offers the advantage of a stable persona, unaffected by real-world events, thus ensuring a consistently neutral baseline perception among participants. Real video clips served as the *Baseline*, against which we reconstructed stylized virtual agents and synthesized voices. We employed a 3×2 within-subjects design with *Style* and *Voice* as independent variables, as summarized in Table 1.

Independent Variable	Level
<i>Style</i>	<i>Hand-sculpted</i>
	<i>AI-reconstructed</i>
	<i>Non-stylized</i>
<i>Voice</i>	<i>Cloned</i>
	<i>Synthesized</i>

Table 1: Experimental Conditions

The *Style* factor includes three levels:

- **Hand-sculpted:** a manually sculpted Sheldon agent model using traditional 3D modeling techniques.
- **AI-reconstructed:** a Sheldon agent model reconstructed from a single image or video clip using data-driven algorithms.
- **Non-stylized:** a plain agent model without any visual features resembling Sheldon.

Figure 1 illustrates Sheldon’s authentic appearance in the baseline video alongside the three different visual styles. Visual similarity to Sheldon was highest for the *Hand-sculpted* agent, whose features were finely reproduced by an expert modeler. The *AI-reconstructed* agent captured the overall facial contour but lacked detail in specific features (e.g., the eyes, nose, and mouth), placing it at an intermediate level. The *Non-stylized* agent, devoid of Sheldon’s distinctive traits, showed the lowest resemblance.

The *Voice* factor includes two levels:

- **Cloned:** voice generated by an AI model that mimics Sheldon’s vocal characteristics, such as timbre, pitch, etc.
- **Synthesized:** voice generated using a conventional TTS tool without specific vocal characteristics.

The *Cloned* voice more faithfully reproduces Sheldon’s vocal traits, yielding greater authenticity than the standard *Synthesized* voice.

Based on the objectives and design of the research, we formulate the following hypotheses.

- **H1:** Style will significantly affect participants’ levels of trust, perceived realism, familiarity, and social presence.
- **H1.1:** *Hand-sculpted* agent will receive the highest ratings in trustworthiness, realism, familiarity, and social presence due to its fine-grained artistic control over details.
- **H2:** Voice type will significantly affect participants’ levels of trust, perceived realism, familiarity, and social presence.

- **H2.1:** *Cloned* voice will receive the highest ratings in trustworthiness, realism, familiarity, and social presence due to its naturalness and close resemblance to the original voice.
- **H3:** The *Hand-sculpted* agent with a *Cloned* voice will be perceived as the closest match, yet perceptions will still differ significantly from the *Baseline* video.
- **H4:** Reduced interpersonal distance will correlate positively with higher trust levels, with the smallest distance expected under the *Hand-sculpted* style or the *Cloned* voice conditions.

3.2 Stimuli Creation

Based on the experiment design, we created the experimental stimuli in a strictly controlled pipeline that produced one baseline video and six derived conditions. Figure 2 illustrates the pipeline for creating the AI-reconstructed agent and driving its facial expressions based on voice as an example.

Fig. 2: A pipeline for creating the *AI-reconstructed* virtual celebrity agent and generating facial expressions based on audio input.

Baseline Selection We selected a 50s video clip from The Big Bang Theory (Season 2, Episode 6) featuring Sheldon’s welcome speech with minimal cuts and close-ups. To keep focus on Sheldon’s face, the video was cropped to show only his upper chest and above. Considering that the original footage was filmed some time ago and had relatively low resolution (1080p), we applied 4 times super-resolution processing to enhance the clarity of Sheldon’s facial features. The processed video served as the baseline and was subsequently used to reconstruct the stylized Sheldon agents.

Celebrity Agent Creation To construct the Hand-sculpted Sheldon, a high-resolution frame providing a clear frontal view of his face was extracted from the baseline video and employed as a reference image. An experienced 3D modeler then sculpted the facial model based on this reference. The model was required to be compatible with MetaHuman¹ in terms of facial blendshapes and skeletal rigging. We adopted the same approach as Gao et al. [18] to get the *AI-reconstructed* Sheldon (see Figure 2). The same reference image was used to generate a facial mesh capturing Sheldon’s facial features, which was then converted into a MetaHuman-compatible model using the Mesh to MetaHuman tool. We selected the MetaHuman preset model *Myles* as the *Non-stylized* Sheldon, ensuring that his facial appearance had no stylistic resemblance to the original character. To isolate facial geometry as the only variable, hair, skin, clothing, and materials were standardized across agents (see Figure 1). These attributes were also matched as closely as possible to those observed in the baseline video.

Voice Synthesis From the same episode, 190 seconds of Sheldon’s speech were extracted, segmented, and denoised to fine-tune GPT-SoVITS [47] for voice cloning, ensuring a higher quality than zero-shot cloning. Based on the transcript of the baseline video, we employed the fine-tuned model to generate *Cloned* speech, adjusting parameters such as speech rate to ensure that the duration of the generated audio closely matched the video baseline. For generating *Synthesized* voice, we employed Microsoft Azure Speech² services with the default middle-aged male voice profile “Guy”. Speech Synthesis Markup Language (SSML) was applied to control pauses and rates, ensuring that the overall duration also closely matched the video baseline.

¹<https://www.metahuman.com/>

²<https://azure.microsoft.com/en-US/products/ai-services/ai-speech/>

Lip-Sync and Facial Expression Lip-sync animation and facial expressions were generated using NVIDIA Omniverse Audio2Face³. A Python script was used to call the API of Audio2Face’s headless version to control the initiation and termination of lip-sync generation and audio playback. Facial expressions were also automatically generated by Audio2Face, with the preferred expression parameter set to *joy* to ensure consistency with the spoken content. The resulting animation frames were exported as BlendShapes and streamed in real-time to Unreal Engine via the Live Link plugin. A TCP connection was established between Unreal Engine and the Python script. By sending a binary flag, the script was able to toggle the agent’s facial state between a neutral smiling pose and a fully synchronized lip with facial expressions.

Virtual Environment The processed baseline video was played directly as material on a plane using the VideoPlayer component. The participant’s initial view under this condition is shown in Figure 3 (a). For the agents, we extracted the first frame, inpainted Sheldon out, and used the resulting clean background as a plane behind the agents. The virtual camera was placed to focus on the face of the agent, minimizing the need for movement of the participants. Figure 3 (b) illustrates an example of the participant’s initial field of view. The scene was illuminated using four point lights arranged around the plane with equal intensity. In order to enhance the sense of immersion, no global illumination was applied.

Fig. 3: Participant’s initial field of view. (a) The *Baseline* video rendered on a VideoPlayer. (b) The *Hand-sculpted* Sheldon agent with a smile, placed in front of the background image.

3.3 Measures

Trust was assessed using the Multidimensional Measure of Trust (MDMT) questionnaire [4, 59], which includes four dimensions: *Capable*, *Ethical*, *Sincere*, and *Reliable*. *Voice Quality* was evaluated with the MOS-X questionnaire [4, 41], covering *Intelligibility*, *Naturalness*, *Prosody*, *Social Impression*, and an *Overall* score. Following Higgins et al. [20], we further evaluated *Perceived Realism* across four dimensions: *Appearance*, *Facial Expression*, *Voice*, and *Overall*. These four dimensions, together with *Personality*, were also used to evaluate *Perceived Familiarity*. *Social Presence* was also measured using the questionnaire proposed by Higgins et al [20]. All questionnaires employed a 7-point Likert scale.

Interpersonal Distance was recorded using the distance between the user’s virtual camera and the agent at 50Hz. Its variation served as an indicator of user trust [7, 11, 46].

3.4 Participants and Apparatus

To ensure familiarity with Sheldon, participants self-rated their knowledge of *The Big Bang Theory* and the character on a 5-point scale (1 = completely unfamiliar, 5 = very familiar). We only included the data of those participants who answered this question with 2 or more in our final analysis. This assured us that the data is homogeneous and represents every participant who has some degree of familiarity with Sheldon, supporting the formation of parasocial relationships. A priori power analysis (G*Power 3.1.9.7) for the 3x2 within-subjects design indicated a minimum of 19 participants (Effect size $f = 0.25$, $\alpha = 0.05$, $power = 0.8$) [12]. We recruited 30 participants (16 female, 14 male; Mean = 25.63, SD = 3.91), ensuring sufficient statistical power. Participants included three from Pakistan, one from Russia, one from Vietnam, and the remainder from China. All participants reported sufficient English listening proficiency to understand the speech content. Among the

³<https://docs.nvidia.com/omniverse/index.html>

participants, four had VR experience, three had used VR devices only in non-immersive contexts (e.g., games), and two reported a history of mild VR sickness. This study was conducted in compliance with ethical guidelines and was approved by the Tsinghua University Science and Technology Ethics Committee (IRB Protocol: THU-03-2024-0022). In line with this, all data were used solely for research purposes, and AI technologies with ethical sensitivities (e.g., voice cloning, facial reconstruction) were strictly confined to the study, with no commercial application or public dissemination.

The experiment ran on a Windows PC equipped with an Intel i7-12700 CPU, an NVIDIA RTX 3090 GPU, and 32 GB of RAM. The VR content was displayed on a Meta Quest 3 via Quest Link. The system was implemented using Unreal Engine 5.4.4, with Python scripts for automation, and NVIDIA Audio2Face (Version 2023.02) for lip-sync and expression generation.

3.5 Procedure

Upon arrival, participants were first asked to sign an informed consent form and complete a demographic questionnaire. They then received a general study briefing (without details of specific conditions) and were instructed to role-play as a Caltech graduate student watching Sheldon’s welcome speech. They were asked to minimize head movements and pay close attention to Sheldon’s appearance, lip synchronization, and facial expressions. All participants started with the baseline, and the other six conditions followed in Latin Square order. Once participants entered the VR environment, they could initiate the speech by pressing the trigger button on the right controller. After each condition, participants were asked to complete the corresponding questionnaires based on their perceptions. Participants were explicitly informed that they could pause or quit at any time if they felt uncomfortable. Before the formal experiment, a 5-minute training session was provided to allow participants to familiarize themselves with the VR headset and its controllers. The entire experiment lasted about 30–40 minutes.

4 RESULTS

To analyze the results, we first conducted analyses of variance (ANOVA) to examine the effects of *Style* and *Voice* on the questionnaire responses. We then identified the combination of *Style* and *Voice* for each dimension that yielded the highest mean scores and compared it with the baseline to quantify the differences between virtual agents and video representation. Finally, we analyzed the changes in participants’ interpersonal distance across all virtual agent conditions.

4.1 Effects of Style and Voice on User Perceptions

A two-way Repeated Measures ANOVA (RM ANOVA) was performed to determine the effects of *Style* and *Voice*. The normality and homogeneity of variance were examined using the Shapiro–Wilk test and Levene’s test. Greenhouse–Geisser corrections were applied when sphericity was violated, and Aligned Rank Transform (ART) ANOVA [62] was used as a non-parametric alternative. Post-hoc comparisons for significant main effects were performed based on the estimated marginal means (EMMs) using Tukey’s HSD adjustment. Table 2 summarizes all significant effects, with full results provided in the Supplementary Materials. All η_p^2 values exceeded Cohen’s threshold for a small effect (0.01) [12]. Their distribution was: 3 below medium (0.06), 7 in the moderate-to-large range, and 6 large (>0.14).

4.1.1 Trust

Style affected selected trust dimensions, while *Voice* showed no significant effects. Figure 4 and Figure 5 illustrate the mean scores (\pm SD) and significant differences across style and voice conditions.

Capable A significant main effect of *Style* was observed. Post-hoc comparisons revealed that the *Hand-sculpted* agent was rated as more capable than the *AI-reconstructed* agent ($p = 0.036$). No significant differences were found between the other pairs (*Hand-sculpted* vs. *Non-stylized*: $p = 0.102$; *AI-reconstructed* vs. *Non-stylized*: $p = 0.900$). No significant main effect of *Voice* was found.

Ethical and Sincere No significant main effects or interaction effects were found.

Measure	Statistical Method	Item	Effect	F	η_p^2	p
Trust	ART ANOVA	<i>Capable</i>	<i>Style</i>	$F(2.00, 145.00) = 3.287$	0.043	0.040*
	RM ANOVA	<i>Reliable</i>	<i>Style</i>	$F(1.93, 55.89) = 3.376$	0.104	0.043*
Voice Quality	RM ANOVA	<i>Intelligibility</i>	<i>Voice</i>	$F(1.00, 29.00) = 21.253$	0.423	< 0.001***
Perceived Realism	ART ANOVA	<i>Appearance</i>	<i>Style</i>	$F(2.00, 145.00) = 3.287$	0.156	0.040*
		<i>Facial Expression</i>	<i>Style</i>	$F(2.00, 145.00) = 11.606$	0.138	< 0.001***
		<i>Voice</i>	<i>Voice</i>	$F(1.00, 145.00) = 19.817$	0.120	< 0.001***
		<i>Overall</i>	<i>Style</i>	$F(2.00, 145.00) = 11.598$	0.138	< 0.001***
		<i>Overall</i>	<i>Voice</i>	$F(1.00, 145.00) = 9.803$	0.063	0.002**
Perceived Familiarity	ART ANOVA	<i>Appearance</i>	<i>Style</i>	$F(2.00, 145.00) = 44.645$	0.381	< 0.001***
		<i>Voice</i>	<i>Voice</i>	$F(1.00, 145.00) = 26.529$	0.155	< 0.001***
		<i>Facial Expression</i>	<i>Style</i>	$F(2.00, 145.00) = 11.808$	0.140	< 0.001***
		<i>Personality</i>	<i>Style</i>	$F(2.00, 145.00) = 6.258$	0.080	0.003**
		<i>Overall</i>	<i>Voice</i>	$F(1.00, 145.00) = 8.138$	0.053	0.005**
		<i>Overall</i>	<i>Style</i>	$F(2.00, 145.00) = 14.471$	0.166	< 0.001***
Social Presence	RM ANOVA	<i>Social Presence</i>	<i>Style</i>	$F(1.89, 54.77) = 10.537$	0.267	< 0.001***

Table 2: Summary of all significant effects (* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$).

Fig. 4: Mean *Trust* ratings grouped by *Style*.

Fig. 5: Mean *Trust* ratings grouped by *Voice*.

Reliable A significant main effect of *Style* was found. However, post-hoc comparisons revealed no significant pairwise differences between the three conditions (*Hand-sculpted* vs. *Non-stylized*: $p = 0.798$; *Hand-sculpted* vs. *AI-reconstructed*: $p = 0.091$; *AI-reconstructed* vs. *Non-stylized*: $p = 1.000$). No significant main effect of *Voice* was found.

4.1.2 Voice Quality

Overall, only *Intelligibility* was significantly affected by *Voice*, whereas no significant effects were observed for *Naturalness*, *Social Impression*, or *Overall* ratings. Figure 6 and Figure 7 present the mean scores (\pm SD) and significant differences across style and voice conditions.

Intelligibility A significant main effect of *Voice* was found. The *Synthesized* voice was rated as more intelligible than the *Cloned* voice ($p < 0.001$).

Naturalness, Social Impression and Overall No significant main effects or interaction effects were observed.

4.1.3 Perceived Realism

Overall, *Perceived Realism* was significantly influenced by both *Style* and *Voice*, with *Hand-sculpted* agents and the *Cloned* voice consistently rated as more realistic. Figure 8 and Figure 7 show the mean scores (\pm SD) and significant differences across style and voice conditions.

Appearance A significant main effect of *Style* was observed. Both the *Hand-sculpted* and *AI-reconstructed* agents were rated as more realistic compared to the *Non-stylized* agent (*Hand-sculpted* vs. *Non-stylized*: $p < 0.001$; *AI-reconstructed* vs. *Non-stylized*: $p = 0.006$), while no significant difference was found between the *Hand-sculpted* and the *AI-reconstructed* agents ($p = 0.211$).

Facial Expression *Style* exhibited a significant main effect. The facial expressions of *Hand-sculpted* were rated as more realistic than those of the *Non-stylized* agent ($p < 0.001$). No significant differences were observed for other pairwise comparisons (*Hand-sculpted* vs. *AI-reconstructed*: $p = 0.051$; *Non-stylized* vs. *AI-reconstructed*: $p =$

Fig. 6: Mean Voice Quality ratings grouped by Style.

Fig. 7: Mean Voice Quality ratings grouped by Voice.

Fig. 8: Mean Perceived Realism ratings grouped by Style.

Fig. 9: Mean Perceived Realism ratings grouped by Voice.

0.061).

Voice A significant main effect of *Voice* was found. The *Cloned* voice was rated as more realistic than the *Synthesized* voice ($p < 0.001$).

Overall Both *Style* and *Voice* had significant main effects. Post-hoc comparisons mirrored the trends observed in the *Appearance* and *Voice* dimensions: the *Hand-sculpted* and *AI-reconstructed* agents were rated as more realistic than the *Non-stylized* agent (*Hand-sculpted* vs. *Non-stylized*: $p < 0.001$; *AI-reconstructed* vs. *Non-stylized*: $p = 0.008$), with no significant difference between the *Hand-sculpted* and the *AI-reconstructed* agents ($p = 0.245$). Moreover, the *Cloned* voice was perceived as more realistic than the *Synthesized* voice ($p = 0.031$).

4.1.4 Perceived Familiarity

Perceived Familiarity was significantly influenced by both *Style* and *Voice*. *Hand-sculpted* and *AI-reconstructed* agents received higher appearance ratings than *Non-stylized*, while the *Cloned* voice was rated higher than *Synthesized* in *Voice* and *Overall*. Compared to *Perceived Realism*, this evaluation included an additional *Personality* dimension. The results are shown in [Figure 10](#) and [Figure 11](#).

Appearance A significant main effect of *Style* was observed. Participants reported the highest familiarity with the *Hand-sculpted* agent compared to both the *AI-reconstructed* and *Non-stylized* agents (*Hand-sculpted* vs. *AI-reconstructed*: $p < 0.001$; *Hand-sculpted* vs. *Non-*

Fig. 10: Mean *Perceived Familiarity* ratings grouped by *Style*.

Fig. 11: Mean *Perceived Familiarity* ratings grouped by *Voice*.

stylized: $p < 0.001$). Moreover, the *AI-reconstructed* agent was rated as more familiar than the *Non-stylized* agent ($p < 0.001$).

Facial Expression Only *Style* showed a significant main effect. Post-hoc comparisons revealed that both the *AI-reconstructed* and *Hand-sculpted* agents’ facial expressions were rated as more familiar than those of the *Non-stylized* agent (*Hand-sculpted* vs. *Non-stylized*: $p < 0.001$; *AI-reconstructed* vs. *Non-stylized*: $p = 0.012$). No significant differences were found between the *Hand-sculpted* and *AI-reconstructed* agents ($p = 0.115$).

Voice A significant main effect of *Voice* was found. The *Cloned* voice was rated higher than the *Synthesized* voice ($p < 0.001$).

Personality Both *Style* and *Voice* had significant main effects. Participants perceived the *AI-reconstructed* and *Hand-sculpted* agents as better reflecting Sheldon’s personality compared to the *Non-stylized* agent (*AI-reconstructed* vs. *Non-stylized*: $p = 0.039$; *Hand-sculpted* vs. *Non-stylized*: $p = 0.001$). No significant differences were found between the *AI-reconstructed* and *Hand-sculpted* agents ($p = 0.452$). Furthermore, the *Cloned* voice better captured Sheldon’s traits compared to the *Synthesized* voice ($p = 0.036$).

Overall Both *Style* and *Voice* had significant main effects. Post-hoc comparisons for style mirrored the *Appearance* results: the *Hand-sculpted* agent was rated as the most familiar overall compared to both the *AI-reconstructed* and *Non-stylized* agents (*Hand-sculpted* vs. *AI-reconstructed*: $p = 0.003$; *Hand-sculpted* vs. *Non-stylized*: $p < 0.001$), while the *AI-reconstructed* agent was rated higher than the *Non-stylized* agent ($p = 0.050$). For *Voice*, results were also consistent with the *Voice* and *Personality* dimensions: agents with the *cloned* voice were rated as more familiar than those with the *Synthesized* voice ($p = 0.003$).

4.1.5 Social Presence

Social Presence was significantly affected by *Style*, with *Hand-sculpted* and *AI-reconstructed* agents rated higher than the *Non-stylized* agent. *Voice* had no significant main effect. Figure 12 shows the mean scores (\pm SD) and significant differences across style and voice conditions.

A significant main effect of *Style* was observed. Participants reported higher *Social Presence* when viewing the *Hand-sculpted* or *AI-reconstructed* agents compared to the *Non-stylized* agent (*Hand-sculpted* vs. *Non-stylized*: $p = 0.009$; *AI-reconstructed* vs. *Non-stylized*: $p < 0.001$). No significant differences were found between the *Hand-sculpted* and *AI-reconstructed* conditions ($p = 0.539$). *Voice* had no significant effects on *Social Presence*.

Fig. 12: Mean *Social Presence* ratings grouped by *Style* (left) and *Voice* (right).

4.2 Comparison of User Perceptions Between Agents and Baseline Video

For each dimension, the non-baseline condition with the highest mean was compared to the baseline using independent-sample t tests or Mann-Whitney U tests, depending on data distribution. Effect sizes were calculated as Cohen’s d (d) for t-tests and the rank-biserial correlation (r) for Mann-Whitney U tests (see Table 3 for details). All significant t-test effects were at least medium ($d > 0.5$), with most being large ($d > 0.8$), except for three comparisons [12]. All Mann-Whitney U test effects were large ($r > 0.5$) [12].

The *Hand-sculpted* agent combined with the *Cloned* voice received the highest ratings across all measures except *Intelligibility*, though still significantly below the Baseline. In contrast, for *Intelligibility*, the *AI-reconstructed* agent paired with the *Synthesized* voice scored highest, showing no significant difference from the Baseline ($p = 0.743$).

4.3 Analysis of Interpersonal Distance

Behavioral data were analyzed by computing average changes in interpersonal distance within 0–45 seconds for each condition. Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) was employed to visualize the distributions of these changes. Figure 13 presents the KDE plots of the average changes in participants’ interpersonal distance grouped by *style* and *voice*. In these plots, denser red areas indicate a higher concentration of distance changes, and the color scale bar specifies the density values. Across all conditions, participants exhibited a general tendency to move

Measure	Item	Sheldon’s 3D Agent		Baseline		Statistics	Effect Size	<i>p</i>
		Style	Voice	Mean(SD)	Mean(SD)			
Trust	Capable	Hand-sculpted	Clone	4.173(1.299)	5.027(0.984)	$t(58) = -2.868$	$ d = 0.741$	$p = 0.006^{**}$
	Ethical	Hand-sculpted	Clone	4.147(1.422)	5.020(0.831)	$t(58) = -2.904$	$ d = 0.750$	$p = 0.006^{**}$
	Sincere	Hand-sculpted	Clone	4.087(1.474)	5.340(0.898)	$t(58) = -3.977$	$ d = 1.027$	$p < 0.001^{***}$
	Reliable	Hand-sculpted	Clone	3.860(1.578)	4.893(1.145)	$t(58) = -2.903$	$ d = 0.750$	$p = 0.005^{**}$
Voice Quality	Intelligibility	AI-reconstructed	Synthesized	5.183(0.873)	5.117(0.685)	$t(58) = 0.329$	$ d = 0.085$	$p = 0.743$
	Naturalness	Hand-sculpted	Clone	4.658(1.234)	5.833(0.816)	$t(58) = -4.350$	$ d = 1.123$	$p < 0.001^{***}$
	Prosody	Hand-sculpted	Clone	4.422(1.462)	5.533(1.053)	$t(58) = -3.378$	$ d = 0.872$	$p = 0.001^{***}$
	Social Impression	Hand-sculpted	Clone	4.117(1.541)	5.675(0.886)	$t(58) = -4.802$	$ d = 1.240$	$p < 0.001^{***}$
	Overall	Hand-sculpted	Clone	4.516(1.172)	5.540(0.680)	$U = 205.500$	$ r = 0.543$	$p < 0.001^{***}$
Perceived Realism	Appearance	Hand-sculpted	Clone	3.600(1.653)	6.233(0.858)	$U = 83.500$	$ r = 0.814$	$p < 0.001^{***}$
	Facial Expression	Hand-sculpted	Clone	3.567(1.813)	6.133(1.008)	$U = 112.000$	$ r = 0.523$	$p < 0.001^{***}$
	Voice	Hand-sculpted	Clone	4.433(1.736)	6.333(0.802)	$U = 161.500$	$ r = 0.751$	$p < 0.001^{***}$
	Overall	Hand-sculpted	Clone	3.667(1.561)	6.267(0.868)	$U = 80.000$	$ r = 0.641$	$p < 0.001^{***}$
	Appearance	Hand-sculpted	Clone	3.833(1.556)	6.233(0.858)	$U = 93.000$	$ r = 0.793$	$p < 0.001^{***}$
Perceived Familiarity	Voice	Hand-sculpted	Clone	3.800(1.710)	6.200(0.847)	$U = 108.500$	$ r = 0.759$	$p < 0.001^{***}$
	Facial Expression	Hand-sculpted	Clone	3.367(1.691)	6.167(0.874)	$U = 86.000$	$ r = 0.809$	$p < 0.001^{***}$
	Personality	Hand-sculpted	Clone	3.567(1.524)	6.167(0.949)	$U = 77.000$	$ r = 0.829$	$p < 0.001^{***}$
	Overall	Hand-sculpted	Clone	4.028(1.483)	6.111(1.166)	$U = 78.000$	$ r = 0.827$	$p < 0.001^{***}$
	Social Presence	Social Presence	Hand-sculpted	Clone	3.193(1.346)	4.407(1.227)	$t(58) = -3.650$	$ d = 0.942$

Table 3: Comparisons of user perceptions between the baseline video and the highest-scoring agent for each questionnaire item (* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$).

Fig. 13: KDE plots of changes in participants’ interpersonal distance within 0–45 seconds (Left: grouped by Style; Right: grouped by Voice).

away from the Sheldon agent.

For *Style*, the *Hand-sculpted* agent elicited the largest mean distance change ($Mean = -0.267, SD = 0.079$), with peaks concentrated around 25s and 40s. The *AI-reconstructed* agent yielded the smallest mean change ($Mean = -0.198, SD = 0.0854$), with data clustered around 20s. The *Non-stylized* agent fell in between ($Mean = -0.254, SD = 0.0779$), with data concentrated around 15s. A Kruskal-Wallis test revealed a significant effect of style ($H = 1281.924, p < 0.001$), with Dunn’s post-hoc tests confirming significant differences in all pairwise comparisons ($p < 0.001$ for all).

For *Cloned* voice, the changes of interpersonal distance ($M = -0.223, SD = 0.079$) were distributed around 15s and 40s. Under the *Synthesized* voice, participants showed a stronger tendency to move away from the agent ($M = -0.256, SD = 0.078$), with data concentrated around 20s and 30s. A Mann-Whitney U test confirmed that the tendency to move away was significantly more pronounced with the *Synthesized* voice ($U = 3367977.500, p < 0.001$).

5 DISCUSSION

This section discusses how our findings inform trust and related perceptions in celebrity virtual agents. We first examine the roles of *Style* and *Voice*, then compare audio-visual matches with the real-video Baseline, and finally assess interpersonal distance as a behavioral indicator of trust in VR.

5.1 How Do Style and Voice Affect Trust and Related Perceptions?

Style exhibited significant main effects on *Trust*, *Perceived Realism*, *Perceived Familiarity*, and *Social presence*. As a result, **H1** was supported. The *Hand-sculpted* agent received higher ratings than the other two styles across all dimensions, except for *Capable*. **H1.1** was partially verified. *Voice* only had a significant main effect on *Perceived Realism* and *Perceived Familiarity*. In contrast, **H2** was not supported, which also led to the rejection of **H2.1**.

Style drove trust in celebrity agents with AI-cloned voices, while *Voice* showed only limited impact. Prior research has demonstrated that *Style*, rather than *Voice*, plays a decisive role in shaping user trust in conventional, non-celebrity virtual agents [18]. Extending this line of work, our study shows that the same pattern holds for celebrity agents paired with high-fidelity AI-based voice cloning, indicating that the influence of *Style* on trust is robust in the settings of both ordinary and celebrity virtual agents, while the role of *Voice* appears more limited. However, post-hoc comparisons revealed that the *Hand-sculpted* style only significantly outperformed *AI-reconstructed* in the *Capable* dimension, while no significant differences were observed in *Reliable*. These results suggest that these three styles may not diverge strongly in their influence on user trust when examined at a finer-grained level. While recent research links photorealistic styles in serious contexts to enhanced perceptions of competence and reliability [22], our experiment context, a formal school orientation speech by

Sheldon, found that visual realism did not affect these perceptions. A potential explanation lies in parasocial relationships [40], the one-sided connections where users treat celebrities as part of their social circle, which may moderate the impact of visual cues. Previous studies have shown that such parasocial relationships enhance familiarity with celebrity agents, which in turn promotes trust [53]. Since all participants in our study were already familiar with Sheldon to varying degrees, the experimental interaction may have further reinforced this relationship, ultimately moderating the differences in trust across agent styles. While the high credibility of AI-driven celebrity digital humans is powerful, it must be met with caution. Implementing reliable watermarking and establishing clear regulations are essential to safeguard against the exploitation of this trust in criminal activities like telecom fraud.

Style shaped key user perceptions, whereas *Voice* exerted only minor effects. Specifically, *Style* significantly affected the perceived realism and familiarity of *Appearance*, *Facial Expressions*, and *overall* impressions, while *Voice* affected only *Voice* and *Overall* realism and familiarity. These results are intuitive and align well with the semantic dimensions of our measures, thereby reinforcing the validity of the experimental design. Moreover, post-hoc comparisons revealed no significant differences between the *Hand-sculpted* and *AI-reconstructed* styles, except for *Appearance Familiarity*, indicating the promising potential of the AI-based reconstruction method for creating virtual agents. With respect to *Personality* familiarity, prior research using public speech tasks has shown that both behavioral and vocal realism can alter participants' perceptions of the Big Five personality traits of agents [55]. Our findings further corroborate this effect in a broader context. Finally, *Style* also significantly influenced *Social Presence*, with the *Hand-sculpted* style receiving the highest ratings, consistent with earlier studies conducted in immersive VR environments [65].

5.2 How Do the Audio-Visual Matches Differ from the Baseline?

The best-performing combination was the *Cloned* voice with the *Hand-sculpted* agent, which achieved the highest ratings across most dimensions (except for *Intelligibility*). However, the ratings under this condition still fell significantly below those of the *Baseline*, highlighting the persistent perceptual gap between celebrity agents and real video-based representations. Thus, **H3** was confirmed.

According to evolutionary psychology, congruence in audiovisual realism signals fitness, promotes subconscious recognition, and reduces cognitive conflict by fulfilling the brain's expectations [25, 30]. In our study, the *Hand-sculpted* style (closest facial resemblance) combined with the *Cloned* voice (closest timbre) provided this congruence, which likely led to its superior perceptual ratings. However, when comparing 3D model-based agents with video-based agents, our results demonstrate that video-based agents provide substantially higher perceptual ratings. This confirms that the realism gap noted in prior work on video-based avatars also exists for virtual agents [3, 63]. Given the high computational cost of video-based agents, 3D models remain a more practical alternative in certain applications.

Interestingly, a different pattern emerged for the *Intelligibility*, where the *AI-reconstructed* agent combined with the *Cloned* voice yielded the highest score. One possible explanation is that voice cloning can perfectly replicate the speaker's timbre, including some of Sheldon's accent. Since none of our participants were native English speakers, Sheldon's accent may have introduced slight comprehension difficulties compared to the more standard pronunciation of the synthesized voice, lowering *Intelligibility* ratings for the *Cloned* voice [35]. Moreover, the McGurk effect [32], a cross-modal illusion caused by mismatched lip movements and speech, could have increased perceptual confusion and lowered the *Intelligibility* scores for the *Hand-sculpted* agents.

5.3 How Does Interpersonal Distance Reflect Trust?

Although participants showed a general trend to approach agents in all conditions, the average changes in interpersonal distance under different styles and voices did not align with the corresponding trust levels. **H4** was not supported. This finding suggests that interpersonal distance may not serve as a direct behavioral indicator of trust in the context of agent-mediated interaction.

Interpersonal distance did not reliably indicate trust in our VR setting. A previous study in desktop environments has suggested that higher levels of trust significantly reduce the preferred interpersonal distance of participants [46]. However, a recent research combining both desktop and VR environments indicates that interpersonal distance is not a stable indicator of trust [11]. Our findings are consistent with the latter. A possible explanation is that participants perceived virtual agents as insufficiently realistic, which caused an uncanny valley effect [34]. The VR setting may have amplified this effect, leading participants to adopt a more conservative stance and maintain greater distance [52], consistent with our results, where the *AI-reconstructed* agent showed the smallest average approach behavior. The distance-trust relationship is further complicated by the parasocial relationships. For instance, while fans of Sheldon might wish to get closer, others may maintain a certain distance due to the perceived status and power.

6 LIMITATIONS

This study has several limitations that point to valuable future research. First, the effectiveness of celebrity agents depends on the celebrity's recognizability and personal traits. Our use of a single, atypically quirky character (Sheldon) limits generalizability. Future work should examine how specific celebrity traits influence trust and include a broader range of celebrities. Second, our sample and design have constraints. Participant traits (e.g., personality, cultural background) may affect trust, highlighting the need for more demographically diverse samples. The lack of a non-celebrity control agent also makes it difficult to isolate the celebrity effect. Furthermore, even the *Non-stylized* agent retained residual celebrity cues (e.g., clothing). The participants' parasocial relationships with Sheldon not controlled through baseline assessment nor directly measured after the stimuli, instead inferring it indirectly from metrics like trust and familiarity. Third, methodological and technical refinements are possible. Objective acoustic features (e.g., frequency, power) could be analyzed to link vocal characteristics to trust. The limitations of current AI reconstruction and voice-cloning techniques in capturing fine details may have affected stimulus quality, an issue that advancing technology can mitigate. Finally, employing video see-through techniques could better control confounds in visual comparisons, and incorporating physiological signals could more precisely quantify the relationship between interpersonal distance and trust.

7 CONCLUSION

This study investigated how advanced AI-reconstruction combined with voice cloning techniques affects users' trust in celebrity agents, as well as related perceptions of realism, familiarity, and social presence. Using a clip of Sheldon from *The Big Bang Theory* as the baseline, we created multiple agents of him with different styles and voice conditions and conducted a 3x2 within-subjects experiment. Our results revealed that style significantly influenced trust, while voice did not. Both perceived realism and familiarity were significantly influenced by style and voice, while social presence was only affected by style. Furthermore, a substantial gap remains between 3D-model-based agents and video-based representations. The relationship between interpersonal distance and trust in VR is complex, suggesting that their interplay warrants further study. Our findings not only offer practical insights on leveraging advanced generative AI to design trustworthy virtual celebrity agents, but also provide critical reflections on the associated trust and ethical implications.

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